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Abstract:

A stable marriage is crucial for establishing a prosperous community, but this depends on the psychological well-being of the couples. The present research aimed to study the psychological well-being of couples married in love and arranged marriage setups. Psychological well-being scale were administered among the participants. The samples for the study were 200 (100 love marriages and 100 arranged marriages), also males and females were divided into two groups equally. The result of the present study revealed a significant difference in psychological well-being between couples (love marriage and arranged marriage). Further, the study has shown that there is a significant difference between males and females in psychological well-being. Pertaining to the study, conclusions and limitations have been discussed.

Key Words: Marital Satisfaction, Psychological Well-Being, Couples (Love and Arranged Marriage)

Introduction:

Love, attraction, and affection for the other person are the hallmarks of romantic partnerships. Though they might differ from person to person, romantic relationships frequently contain emotions of commitment, infatuation, and intimacy. Three primary aspects of love were examined by theorist Robert Sternberg (1987): intimacy, passion, and commitment/decision. Intimacy and passion coexist in a romantic partnership. According to reports, love marriages might provide longer-term contentment than arranged unions. According to Snyder and Lopez's 2005 research, happy married people experience less stress and anxiety. Martin (2007), reported that choosing to get married and the several things that impact the marriage and its adaptations should be viewed as a process of growth rather than as a typical life event. Since a marriage does not live in a vacuum, it must go through emotional, physical, and psychological phases. According to Patrick, Sells, Giordano, and Tollerud (2007), the majority of marriages exhibit a U-shaped pattern in which couples experience high levels of marital satisfaction in their early years of marriage, a decline following the birth of their children, and then another increase when the children move out. Peleg (2008) found that marital satisfaction is significantly influenced by the length of a marriage.

Family happiness is directly correlated with the length of a marriage. Gender is a significant factor in the adjustment and contentment of marriage. According to a research by Guo and Huang (2005), men reported being more satisfied with martial arts than women. In 2004, Yuji, K., Junich, T., Ikuo, D., and Masanori, I. examined the degree of marital satisfaction among Chinese women in self-marriage and planned marriages. Numerous factors were considered, including the dominating role in selecting a mate, dating a spouse before marriage, the number of romantic relationships, the depth of one's feelings of love after marriage, etc. Regardless of how long the marriage lasted, self-married women were shown to be happier than those in arranged marriages. Shachar (1991), concluded that marital pleasure is not just based on the type of marriage (self- or arranged). In 2004, Yuji, K., Junich, T., Ikuo, D., and Masanori, I. examined the degree of marital satisfaction among Chinese women in self-marriage and planned marriages. Numerous factors were considered, including the dominating role in selecting a mate, dating a spouse before marriage, the number of romantic relationships, the depth of one's feelings of love after marriage, etc. According to Allendorf and Ghimire (2013), couples that chose self-marriage experienced greater levels of marital happiness. In a survey on marital satisfaction, Madathil and Benshoff (2008) separated the sample into three groups: self-marriages in the US, arranged marriages in India, and arranged marriage couples residing in the US.

Affection, loyalty, financial stability, and shared ideals were among the considerations. The study found that US couples who opted for an arranged marriage experienced better levels of marital satisfaction than either self-marriage or an arranged marriage in India. In the US, love-marriage couples valued loyalty above all else, while arranged marriage couples valued love above all else. Additionally, it was observed that Indian and American arranged marriage couples placed a great value on financial stability because these aspects of Indian culture are deeply ingrained in Indian culture. Positivity, or feeling good about oneself, or the lack of negativity are the two components of psychological well-being. by Carol Ryff defined. Her six criteria for psychological well-being are as follows: an individual must possess autonomy, environmental mastery, personal growth, positive interpersonal relationships, and a sense of purpose in life. It has been discovered that psychological well-being, which is a crucial component of the partnership and plays a significant role in maintaining stability in them, has been the primary worry in having a stable relationship (Statistica, 2024). Marital stability cannot be attained without psychological well-being (Olarfsson & Steingrimsdottir, 2020). Higher psychological well-being is associated with better marital satisfaction, stability, longevity, physical health, decreased feelings of loneliness, and other positive outcomes. Marital happiness is the biggest factor influencing married people's total satisfaction, according to Ondingi and Mugenda (2011). Therefore, the present study is designed to investigate the difference between couples in love marriage and arranged marriage in terms of psychological well-being.

Significance of the Study:

A study examining psychological well-being and marital adjustment among love and arranged marriage couples holds significant implications for understanding the complexities of marital relationships in diverse cultural contexts. Another way to challenge preconceptions is to find common ground, debunk falsehoods, and comprehend elements like bias and cultural effects.

Methodology

Research Question:

- How does the type of marriage (love or arranged) influence the psychological well-being of individuals?

Objectives:

- To study the psychological well-being among couples of love and arranged marriage settings
- To study the psychological well-being among male and females

Hypotheses:

- There would be a significant difference in psychological well-being among couples of love and arranged marriage setups
- There would be a significant difference in psychological well-being among male and female

Criteria:

The couples who have married under the concept of love and arranged marriage settings have been considered for the present study.

Samples:

The respondents included in the present study are 100 couples, divided into two groups (love marriage 100 and arranged marriage 100). The respondents were selected through the purposive sampling method from Gulbarga districts.

Research Questionnaire:

The psychological well-being developed by Carol Ryff (2014). It consists of a 42-item designed to measure six theoretically motivated constructs of psychological wellbeing, which are (1) a sense of self-determination (autonomy), (2) the capacity to manage effectively one's life and surrounding world (environmental and mastery), (3) a sense of continued growth and development as a person (personal growth), and (4) the possession of quality relations with others (positive relations with others). (5) Positive evaluation of oneself and one's past life (self-acceptance), and (6) the belief that one's life is purposeful and meaningful (purpose in life). The model's six dimensions come closer to capturing the breadth of psychological well-being, predicated upon the assumption that individuals strive to function fully and to realise their unique talents.

Statistical Techniques:

t - test was carried out to find out the comparative analysis, i.e. love and arranged marriage couples and gender.

Result and Discussion:

Table 1: Shows the mean, SD and t-value of couples of love and arranged marriage in psychological well-being

Factors	Couple With Love Marriage (N=100)		Couple With Arranged Marriage (N=100)		t - Value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Autonomy	17.53	9.21	14.54	6.57	3.49 **
Environmental Mastery	18.70	5.67	17.11	6.45	3.82**
Personal Growth	20.58	6.37	18.22	7.34	4.82**
Positive Relations	21.14	8.26	19.17	6.09	4.02**
Purpose in Life	24.26	9.07	21.12	7.92	5.06**
Self-Acceptance	21.33	4.29	18.35	8.11	7.02**
Overall PSW	123.10	29.20	118.12	19.74	9.24**

Significant at 0.01 level

The above depict that the mean, standard deviation and t-value score of love and arranged marriage married couples in psychological well-being. According to the results, couples who wed in love marriage settings had a higher mean (123.10) than couples who wed in arranged marriage platforms (mean 118.12). The statistical significance (t-9.24) is noteworthy at the 0.01 level. This means that the couples who got engaged and married in love marriage setups have higher levels of psychological well-being. They also have strong environmental factors that support their good mental health, personal growth, and a sense of purpose in life. All of these factors have allowed the couples to lead more autonomous and mutually understanding lives. Additionally, they embrace each other for who they are, which will inevitably help them to comprehend one another.

However, the study found that the means of psychological well-being sub dimensions such as self-acceptance, positive relationships, environmental mastery, autonomy, and personal progress are greater than those of their counterparts. According to the results, couples who have tied the knot in love marriage arrangements are happier than their counterparts on these parameters (purpose in life, positive relations with others and environmental mastery).

Table 2: Shows the mean, SD and t-value of male and female on psychological well-being

Factors	Male (N=100)		Female (N=100)		t - Value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Autonomy	13.53	2.12	16.24	4.57	2.29*
Environmental Mastery	14.10	1.67	16.45	2.41	2.82*
Personal Growth	19.09	6.34	22.58	5.37	3.12*
Positive Relations	12.14	6.86	14.17	5.91	3.021*
Purpose in Life	21.22	8.07	18.12	6.92	5.46*
Self-Acceptance	18.12	6.21	22.43	5.29	8.02**
Overall PSW	118.67	15.71	127.06	21.32	8.24**

Significant at 0.01 level.

Table 2 shows the mean, SD, and t-value of male and female married couples on psychological well-being. The result indicates that there is a significant difference in psychological well-being across genders. Thus, the mean scores suggest that females have a higher sense of psychological well-being as compared to their male counterparts. Hence, the hypothesis that there would be a significant difference in psychological well-being among genders has been accepted. On the other hand, the result has also been reported on the psychological well-being sub-dimensions, such as autonomy, environmental mastery, personal growth,

and self-acceptance, which have been found to be higher in females than males. However, purpose in life showed it is higher in males than females because females sometimes tend to feel emotionally low in terms of bodily. However, females have felt all through their lives that they should better manage themselves in difficult circumstances.

Discussion:

Marriage is a union or an institution; it is a legitimate contract between two individuals on the opposite sex that establishes the rights and commitments between them, and their children as well as their extended family members. The result has been reported that psychological well-being is higher in couples who have married in love marriage settings than the arranged marriage settings. The compatibility in love marriage is more in couples, they may share a romantic companionship, affection, bonding, intimate, freedom etc, but whereas in couples of arranged marriage is seen less in them due to because arranged marriage couples might not be able to find a closeness, intimate or bonding in initial stage, hence this could be the probable reason for not exhibiting a greater level of psychological well-being. Mutual attraction/attachment and love is an important factor in their life (Yalom et al. 2002). Marital factors such as love, intimacy and happiness usually come from marriages of choice rather than arranged marriages. Kaslow and Robinson (1996) mutual trust, mutual respect, mutual support, corresponding religious beliefs, loyalty/fidelity, mutual give and take, similar philosophy of life, enjoyment of shared fun/humor, and shared interests are high in people who have got love marriage.

To oversee the current study result it has clearly provided that couples who have got engaged and married in a love marriage setup have shown higher levels of psychological well-being than their counterparts. It is evident that people having to know each other might create a bond and a kind of intimacy in other person, also it may help them to understand each other's on different backgrounds. Of course, in an arranged marriage setup people will not be able to find autonomy, personal growth and positive relations as compared to people who got married in love marriage settings. also, couples showed higher satisfaction on environmental mastery, here couples of love marriage setups, are easily find the way to reach their destination if in terms of any incompatibility because each other knows their limitations, boundaries, moods, lifestyles etc, all of these may make them to understand their environment. Further, they have a purpose in their life means of planning for the future, doing a job, earning credits, setting up their basic needs etc. Self-acceptance also has a high impact on their life this means accepting the life challenges equally rather than getting tensed or disturbed.

Further, the current study has also reported that females have a higher level of psychological well-being as compared to males. Females have a sense of autonomy in managing their family, relationships, environment, balanced lifestyle, positive relationships and accepting life challenges.

Conclusion:

The study has made a conclusive comment on psychological well-being. It has been found that people who have gotten married in love marriage setups have shown a greater level of autonomy, environmental mastery, purpose in life, positive relations, personal growth, and self-acceptance. Further, the study also reported a gender difference. Females have a better level of autonomy, environmental mastery, personal growth, positive relations, and self-acceptance. Whereas males have exhibited a higher sense of purpose in life than females.

Limitation of the Study:

The current study is limited to a small sample size, and the research was carried out in only the Gulbarga district of north Karnataka. The study did not investigate socio demographic variables.

References:

1. Allendorf, K., & Ghimire, D. J. (2013). Determinants of marital quality in an arranged marriage society. *Social Science Research*, 42(1), 59-70.
2. Guo, B., & Huang, J. (2005). Marital and Sexual Satisfaction in Chinese Families: Exploring the Moderating Effects. *Journal of Sex & Marital Therapy*, 31, 21-29. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/00926230590475224>
3. Kaslow, F. W., & Robison, J. A. (1996). Long-term satisfying marriages: Perceptions of contributing factors. *American Journal of Family Therapy*, 24, 153-170(13) (PDF) Ties that Bind: A Qualitative Study of Happy Long-Term Marriages. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/227123637_ties_that_bind_a_qualitative_study_of_happy_long-term_marriages [accessed Aug 06 2024].
4. Martin, R. A. (2007). An analysis of marital adjustment, optimal religious functioning, and length of marriage among new, continuing, and graduating students and their nonstudent spouses at South-western Baptist Theological Seminary in Fort Worth, Texas (3289562 Ph.D.). Southwestern Baptist Theological Seminary, Ann Arbor. Retrieved from <http://search.proquest.com/docview/304776791?accountid=27932>
5. Olafsson, A., & Steingrimsdottir, H. (2020). Howdoes daddy at home affect marital stability? *The Economic Journal*, 130(629), 1471-1500.
6. Patrick, S., Sells, J. N., Giordano, F. G., & Tollerud, T. R. (2007). Intimacy, differentiation, and personality variables as predictors of marital satisfaction. *The Family Journal*, 15(4), 359-367. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1066480707303754>
7. Peleg, O. (2008). The relation between differentiation of self and marital satisfaction: What can be learned from married people over the course of life? *American Journal of Family Therapy*, 36, 388-401. Routledge. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/01926180701804634>
8. Raina P & Maity T (2018). An Empirical Study on Marital Satisfaction between Arranged and Self Marriage Couples in Bangalore. *International Journal of Indian Psychology*, Vol. 6, (1), DIP: 18.01.033/20180601, DOI: 10.25215/0601.033
9. Ryff, C. D. (2014). Psychological well-being revisited: Advances in the science and practice of eudaimonia. *Psychotherapy and psychosomatics*, 83(1), 10-28 (13) (PDF) The Levels of Psychological Well-Being among Married Couples in Selected Parishes in the Catholic Archdiocese of Nairobi, Kenya. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/379807051_the_levels_of_psychological_well-being_among_married_couples_in_selected_parishes_in_the_catholic_archdiocese_of_nairobi_kenya [accessed Aug 06 2024].
10. Shachar, R. (1991). His and her marital satisfaction: The double standard. *Sex Roles*, 25, 451- 467.

11. Sternberg, R. J. (1987). Liking versus loving: A comparative evaluation of theories. *Psychological Bulletin*, 102 (3), 331.
12. Yalom, I. D. (2002). *The gift of therapy*. New York: Harper Collins
13. Yuji, K., Junich, T., Ikuo, D. and Masanori, I. (2004). Love styles and romantic love experience in Japan". *Social behavior and personality*. 1-8.
14. Yuji, K., Junich, T., Ikuo, D. and Masanori, I. (2004). Love styles and romantic love experience in Japan". *Social behavior and personality*. 1-8.